

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R2.2 3D geometric model with interpreted surfaces and bases of selected horizons, settled wells and fault planes

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CONTENT

1 INTRODUCTION.....	3
2 COMPILATION AND EDITING INPUT DATA INTO THE REQUIRED FORMATS.....	5
2.1 Exploration and production wells data set	5
2.2 Well logs and drilling parameters.....	5
2.3 Geophysical data set	8
3 INTERPRETATION OF SEISMIC DATA.....	10
3.1 Seismic to well tie.....	10
3.2 Seismic interpretation in time domain.....	15
3.3 Time surfaces construction and time-to-depth conversion of key surfaces.....	16
3.4 Seismic horizon mapping (stratigraphic boundaries), time and depth maps	19
4 CONSTRUCTION OF THE FIRST VERSION OF THE 3D STATIC MODEL OF STORAGE COMPLEX.....	22
4.1 Set of depth maps and 3D view.....	22
5 CONCLUSIONS.....	28

1 INTRODUCTION

Construction of a 3D geometric model based on seismic interpretation and well results was the first major task of the whole work package 2 targeting the construction of 3D geological model of the storage complex. The surfaces of most prominent lithostratigraphical units (forming the reservoir and sealing rocks for the Zar-3 CO₂ storage complex) served thus as the main input for the static reservoir model constructed in Petrel software as being then a base for dynamic modelling of CO₂, oil, gas and water behaviour within the storage complex. The flowchart of the 3D geological model construction is in Fig. 1-1.

Fig. 1-1: Flowchart showing the steps in geological model construction.

Most of the necessary input data was obtained mainly from the operator of the Zar-3 oil and gas field, which is MND a.s. Hodonín, and from the CGS – Geofond database. They were mostly processed under WP1 „Data gathering and consolidation”. At the beginning of the task, a basic coordinate system was defined (Czech S-42: EPSG:28403 - S-42 (Pulkovo 1942 / Gauss-Krüger zone 3), to which all data within the project are transferred.

The interpretations were done partly in MND a.s. using the Petrel software by Schlumberger (Slb) and partly in the CGS using the Petrel (Slb), OpendTect and Voxler (Golden Software) programs with contribution to both interpretation versions by the NORCE team. The area where the model was built was chosen in the vicinity of the Zar-3 future CO₂ storage site, where recently oil and gas field is being produced and operated by MND a.s. Two areas of different scale were finally chosen for the interpretations.

Fig. 1-2: The working area for regional simplified geological model (red polygon).

Fig. 1-3: The working area for reservoir model as an input for dynamic reservoir simulation (aquifer and injection zone is highlighted as a depth color surface).

A larger-scale area (Fig. 1-2), used for more regional simplified interpretations of geological units includes the overburden of the CO₂ storage structure defined by the polygon chosen to cover the Zar-3 structure itself and its close vicinity.

A lower-scale area covers the static reservoir model with direct overburden incorporation (Fig. 1-3), chosen to cover mainly the reservoir rock saturated recently by hydrocarbons and its larger aquifer part to allow the best estimation of active aquifer zone during dynamic modelling phase.

For the interpretation of seismic and well data, the latest version of Petrel software by Schlumberger was used.

2 COMPILATION AND EDITING INPUT DATA INTO THE REQUIRED FORMATS

2.1 Exploration and production wells data set

The database which was used for construction of interpreted surfaces and bases of selected horizons, settled wells and fault planes consist mainly from the archival hydrocarbon well data provided by MND a.s. and the 3D seismic cube with chosen coordinates processed and prepared by MND a.s. The hydrocarbon production data provided by MND a.s. were also used for model construction as well as final reports from hydrocarbon wells covering the former geological, paleontological and hydrocarbon origin studies. Those were also used for stratigraphy definition in all involved wells. All those archival data were gathered and saved in CO₂-SPICER repository for further use within the WP1.

The first step was the preparation of geodetic and geological data of 22 wells and sidetracks in the breather area of the Zar-3 field in the EXCEL spreadsheet editor, so that they could be imported into any interpretation software: UH3, UH5, UH6, UH9, UH10, UH11, UH12, UH16, ZA1, ZA3, ZA4, ZA4a, ZA5H, ZA6, ZA6A, ZA7, ZA8AH, ZA8H, ZA9AH, ZA9H, ZA12 and ZA14H.

2.2 Well logs and drilling parameters

All well logs from 22 wells have been digitized by the operator (standard LAS files) and are available in the project database. All well logs are imported into a 3D static geological model. An example is shown in Fig. 2-1.

Fig. 2-1: Example of gamma-ray and resistivity well logs in ZA3 well.

In order to display and correlate drilling parameters in profiles, they have been converted to LAS files, example of the ZA7 well is shown in Fig. 2-2.

Fig. 2-2: Well ZA-7 - drilling parameters in the form of well logs: ROP – rate of penetration, WOB – weight of bit, RPM – revolutions per minute, SPP – stand-pipe pressure, T GAS – trip gas.

2.3 Geophysical data set

The main input for seismic interpretation of all lithostratigraphical units within the area of 3D geometrical model of Zar-3 area was the 3D seismic cube provided by MND a.s. All 3D seismic block in the area were acquired mainly for the hydrocarbon exploration in hydrocarbon licence area. Two 3D acquisition blocks are covering the Zar-3 storage site. The 3D block Uhřice1994 covering directly the Zar-3 area was acquired during the 1993-1994, the 3D block Uhřice east was acquired in 2003. The older Uhřice 94 block was acquired using the dynamite technology, the Uhřice east was acquired using the Vibroseis technology. The basic acquisitions parameters are summed up in Tab. 2-1.

Tab. 2-1: 3D seismic acquisition parameters for the block used in Zar-3 area interpretation

3D seismic block	Uhřice 1994	Uhřice East - north part
Technology	Dynamite	Vibroseis
Recording system	Sercel SN388	I/O System Two
Trace length/Sample interval	5000 ms/2 ms	5000 ms/2 ms
Total number of sources	3882	4685
Source point interval	50 m	50 m
Source line interval	300 m	250 m
Shot hole depth	13 – 54 m	10 – 100 Hz/16 s
Total number of receivers	7506	13539
Receiver interval	50 m	50 m
Receiver line interval	150 m	150 m
Receiver lines	6	12
Active channel per line	60	50
Live channels	360	600
Nominal fold	15	30
Minimum – maximum offset	17 – 2055 m	1 – 1901 m
Total number of traces	1361287	2590298

The raw seismic data were processed in MND a.s. processing centre in Brno in 2018. All blocks were merged and the final grid of processed data has a bin size of 25x25 m. For the final block chosen for the Zar-3 project an area within Inlines 2347 – 2467 and Xlines 2544 – 2744 was chosen with preserved sample interval 2 ms and total time/depth of bottom of seismic bloc at level -4998 ms. The 5D regularization was used for compensation of geometry anomalies caused by irregular positioning of shot points and receivers. Regularized data for prestack time migration results in less unwanted migration effects. The module FRENDD was used for 5D regularization incorporated in Geovation software by CGG used for seismic data processing. For final PreSTM (pre stack time migration) the Kirchhoff method was used in raytrace version with final velocity and anisotropy model incorporated from latest processing versions. The amplitude equalization with operator 2000 ms was applied before migration. Then the RMO – high density “residual moveout” was applied for its correction as it was still present on migrated gathers before stacking. The data were reduced by partial stacks in offset classes with step 150 m and the noise attenuation in tau-p domain was done before automatic

picking RMO. The seismic cube with vertical and deviated well trajectories is shown in Fig. 2-3.

Fig. 2-3: 3D seismic cube with deviated wells of Zar-3 oil and gas field and its surroundings.

Well logs (see chapter 2.2) represent additional geophysical data used for 3D model building. For seismic interpretation, the check-shot (well shoot) data are very important - see chapter 3.1.

3 INTERPRETATION OF SEISMIC DATA

3.1 Seismic to well tie

The first step of seismic time dataset interpretation is seismic to well tie that allows converting the well data set into a time domain. In Zar-3 project basically the ZA3 (Fig. 3-2) and ZA7 (Fig. 3-1) check-shot data were used for basic seismic to well tie directly in the Zar-3 field area while ZA1 check-shot data (Fig. 3-2) were also used for basic seismic to well tie in the area outside of the field.

Fig. 3-1: ZA7 check shot – measured interval velocities (left) and calculated mean velocities vs. depth in the well (right).

Two-way-time in respect to depth curves in wells ZA-1 and ZA-3 provide another basis for conversion of well data from the depth domain into time domain and vice versa (Fig. 3-2).

Fig. 3-2: Well ZA-3 and ZA-1 – results of check-shot survey.

Building the synthetic seismograms was the second step necessary for the proper seismic to well tie process. Seismograms were then correlated with the real seismic trace to set the discrete reflector in 3D seismic related to the stratigraphic boundary known from the well. Sonic and density well logs were imported into the fundamental synthetic seismogram. Then the well logs were edited for despiking (removing spikes) in both logs in order to avoid any artificial events. Then the logs were calibrated using the check-shot data (if available). The acoustic impedance was then calculated either directly from the sonic and density logs, or the sonic log (if not available for given well) was calculated from the density log. From the acoustic impedance the reflection coefficients were derived as the main input for calculation of synthetic seismic trace.

Then, the proper wavelet has been chosen for calculation either using the wavelet extraction or using directly the wavelet parameters in several iterations. In the Zar-3 project two Ricker wavelets were used with peak frequencies of 22 and 28 Hz, with no phases rotation as the 3D seismic cube is expected to be zero phased processed. The ZA3 and ZA4a synthetic traces are demonstrated in Fig. 3-3 and 3-4, where all input

parameters can be observed. The synthetic trace “Synthetic 1” was calculated using 22 Hz Ricker wavelet and the Synthetic 13 was calculated using 28 Hz Ricker wavelet. The Fig. 3-3 and 3-4 shows the types of seismic boundaries for further correlation and seismic interpretation in the intervals of lithostratigraphic changes.

Fig. 3-3: ZA4A – Well logs, acoustic impedance, reflection coefficients and synthetic traces.

Fig. 3-4: ZA7 Well logs, acoustic impedance, reflection coefficients and synthetic traces.

Well logs served as basis for cross-correlation of lithological well profiles. The stratigraphic boundaries given in the final geological reports of the wells were updated, revised and adjusted according to the new correlation. Stratigraphic boundaries were also confirmed by mud logs. A total of 8 correlates were selected, which were processed into correlation schemes and geological profiles (Fig. 3-5).

Fig. 3-5: ZA-3 – well logs, stratigraphy, lithology, core samples, perforations, oil and gas inflow.

3.2 Seismic interpretation in time domain

After seismic data were tied to well data in time domain, detailed geological interpretation of the most recently processed 3D seismic data was performed both in Xline and Inline directions covering the Zar-3 oil and gas field and its vicinity as a future CO₂ storage site. An example of stratigraphy and faults interpretation in a seismic section (Inline 2415) is shown in Fig. 3-6 and Fig. 3-7 (Xline 2830). The seismic horizons chosen for detailed interpretation were the reservoir rocks (top of Vranovice carbonates), reservoir base (top of PreMesozoic) and the sealing overburden of the Zar-3 storage complex built by the Mikulov Fm. (top and base), autochthonous Paleogene (top and base), base of Carpathian Thrust Units and the rocks forming the basement of the Zar-3 reservoir facies – the Lower Carboniferous (top), Devonian carbonate facies (top), Devonian basal clastics (top).

Fig. 3-6: Seismic section along Inline 2415 showing the interpreted surfaces and describing the lithostratigraphical units within ZAR-3 project area.

All interpretations were done mainly in the project area Fig. 1.2 and in case of direct inputs for the static reservoir model also within the model active aquifer Fig 1.3. The seismic interpretation benefited from knowledge of regional geological setting of the area based on experience from the oil and gas exploration works in the Nesvačilka paleo valley basin.

The interpretation of seismic data was done in 3D and standard density of interpretations was performed as each 5th line was interpreted for every surface in inline direction and each 5th line was interpreted for all surfaces in Xline direction (Figs. 3-6 and 3-7). The interpretational grid was increased to 2x2 in both directions in the direct vicinity of the Zar-3 storage area. The faults within the area were also interpreted with the similar grid that was used for the interpretation of key seismic horizons. Some faults were used as a boundary for the static geological model grid and one major fault was detected in the central part of the Vranovice Fm. reservoir area.

Fig. 3-7: Seismic section along Xline 2830 showing the interpreted surfaces and describing the lithostratigraphical units within ZAR-3 project area.

3.3 Time surfaces construction and time-to-depth conversion of key surfaces

From the final interpretational grid (Fig. 3-8) for each key horizon the time surfaces were constructed as the main input for velocity model for its time-to-depth conversion.

Fig. 3-8: Example of final interpretational grid in 3D view. The top of Vranovice Fm. grid with fault pattern.

During surface construction, the grid increment 10x10 m was used with automatic position from the input data. Input data polygons were refined in pre-processing by smooth (cubic spline) algorithm, which kept the original points unchanged. No post-processing was used as the time surfaces were serving as an input for time depth migration in next step. All key surfaces were constructed in the same way. The time surface of the Pre-Mesozoic basement as an example is demonstrated in Fig. 3-9. The interpreted faults were not used for the construction of time surfaces as they were lately depth migrated separately and used as an input for static model construction of the reservoir facies of the Zar-3 field.

Fig. 3-9: The time surface of Pre-Mesozoic grid in 3D view, serving as a base for the reservoir model.

Fig. 3-10: Average velocity map showing the velocities used for the time – depth conversion of the Vranovice Fm. top surface.

The time depth migration was done using the well velocity data in combination with surfaces constructed from time interpreted horizons. During TWT (two-way-time) to Z (depth) conversion, the bi-directional model was used, the depth tolerance was set to 1 m and time tolerance to 4 ms. Increment of final depth surface was set at 20 m in each direction with Convergent interpolation method. Average velocity maps (Fig 3-10) were constructed and the time depth migration was done for all key lithostratigraphic units including the Base of Carpathian thrust units, Top of Pre-Tertiary, Top of Mikulov Fm., Top of Vranovice Fm., Top of Lower Carboniferous, Top of Pre-Mesozoic (Fig. 3-11). Time depth conversion of top of Nikolčice Fm. was done during the zone making process during the pillar gridding of static model.

Fig. 3-11: The resulting depth surfaces used as an input for a static reservoir model after depth migration.

3.4 Seismic horizon mapping (stratigraphic boundaries), time and depth maps

In the above chapters building of stratigraphic boundaries is described based on wells and 3D seismic block. Attention was focused mainly on the surface of the formation. Seismic attributes were also used in the interpretation. Well log correlations tied with seismic data served as basis for geological cross sections, e.g. UH11-ZA7 (Fig. 3-12).

Fig. 3-12: Zar-3 oil and gas field – NNW-SSE geological profile with well logs.

The connecting lines in the seismic profiles correlations are guided, where possible, by continuous reflections, which characterize lithological and/or stratigraphic boundaries of contrasting rock types. The resulting time maps are documented by isolines of two-way-time (ms) converted to depth domain, e.g. Fig. 3-13 and Fig. 3-14.

3D seismic measurements were performed in relatively demanding seismogeological conditions with rapid lithofacial changes, significant layer slopes, discordances and variable seismic wave propagation rates. Some parts are quite difficult to interpret. For this reason, the depth maps were adjusted well data, mud logs and correlations of logging measurements.

Fig. 3-13: Base of the Carpathian thrust belt in time domain.

Fig. 3-14: Base of the Carpathian thrust belt – depth domain.

4 CONSTRUCTION OF THE FIRST VERSION OF THE 3D STATIC MODEL OF STORAGE COMPLEX

4.1 Set of depth maps and 3D view

At this stage, the first version of the 3D geometric model of the storage complex was constructed from a set of depth maps. The version will be gradually supplemented and further developed as the output data from other WPs will grow.

The grids of individual maps are in Z-map + and ASCII files, which can be used in various types of software. A complete set of depth maps of tops, bases and thicknesses of individual formations is documented in the Appendix of the V1 result.

Fig. 4-1: Top of Vranovice Fm. with original oil gas and oil water contacts.

Fig. 4-2: Top of Vranovice Fm. with overlying seal rock units: autochthonous Paleogene (Nesvačilka Fm., Žarošice Mb.) and Upper Jurassic Mikulov Fm.

Fig. 4-3: Base of Vranovice Fm. with original oil-water contact.

Fig. 4-4: 3D view – Top of Vranovice Fm. with original oil-water contact.

It is assumed that there is a connection between the Vranovice Formation and the Nikolčice Formation. Therefore, special maps were constructed on the top of the Vranovice Fm. and, where they are not present, on the top of the Nikolčice Fm.

For the volumes of the aquifer calculation, maps of the thicknesses of the Vranovice Fm. and the Nikolčice Fm. were made in three variants.

Fig. 4-5: Top of Vranovice Fm. and Nikolčice Fm.

Fig. 4-6: Thickness map of the Vranovice and Nikolčice Fms. – whole area.

Fig. 4-7: Thickness map of the Vranovice and Nikolčice Fms. – Eastern part (no connection with North-Eastern part).

Volume of reservoir rocks (m ³) – South-East part			
Gas	Oil	Water	Total
10 462 347	24 561 670	121 432 899	156 456 916

Fig. 4-8: Thickness map of the Vranovice and Nikolčice Fms. – South-Eastern part (no connection with North-Eastern and Eastern part).

5 CONCLUSIONS

- The static 3D geometric model of the Zar-3 oil and gas field and future CO₂ storage complex was built based on well and seismic data and will serve as an input for the dynamic model in WP3.
- Well logs were regionally correlated and tied to seismic data.
- Regional geological cross sections were built and show the sedimentary and tectonic edifice of the Zar-3 field.
- Set of maps of tops, bases and thickness in time and depth domain were constructed based on interpreted well and seismic data.

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